

Agriculture and Rural development

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Abstract –

An Indian Farmer is one of the most important member of the society .He is the provider of food to the people , to all practical purposes . farmer's life is simple . He goes to the field early in the morning with his cattle when the rest of world is sleeping comfortably in their warm beds. He faces all the climate hardships without any complaints . The real India resides in its villages . About 70 % of India's population lives in rural areas and earns its livelihood there . The major occupation of these people is agriculture . Thus Indian economy is totally an agrarian one. However much industrialized india may become farmers will may remain an integral part of the economy ,contributing to 26% of national GDP . Agriculture is the principle source of livelihood for many households in Rural India . As Mahatma Gandhi said ,” India lives in Villages and agriculture is the soul of Indian Economy . Nearly two-thirds of its population depends directly on agriculture for its livelihood. Agriculture is the main stay of Indian Economy . Agriculture meets food requirements of the people and produce several raw material for industries . Agriculture is the real part of sources of government income because there are land revenue ,excise duty on agro based goods ,taxes on production and sale of agriculture machinery contributing national income . Agriculture development is directly related to rural development because in rural area people are depend on agriculture sector . There are many factor which is related to rural development . Contribution in GDP, Largest employment source, promoting Sustainable Livelihood for the poor .

Key Words – livelihood, , Food security ,Sustainable Livelihood .Poverty ,Employment

Introduction

Most of Indian are directly depending on the agriculture . Some are directly attached with the farming and some other people are involved in doing business with these goods .India has the capacity to produce the food grains which can make west different in Indian economy . to achieve targeted mark by the government ,it needs to provide support in case of land banks ,loans and other machineries to the small farmers along with the big farmers as it would bring much improvement in Indian economy .

Rural and agriculture development and equitable distribution of the benefits of economic growth are crucial for the global reduction of poverty and hunger .Numerous Studies have provided evidence that the impact of Indian economic growth and reducing hunger and poverty depends as much on the nature of the growth (e.g. industrial or rural economy based) as on its scale and for example , a world bank analysis a data from India .found that growth in rural areas and in the agriculture sector had a much greater impact on reducing poverty than did urban and industrial growth .

The concept of Rural Development

The concept of rural development conceived as a response to the increasing external pressure on rural communities . In the past ,Rural communities were able to react by increasing Specialization to take advantage of comparative advantages and economies of scale .However ,Globalization and increased competition from other areas in the same country or from another part of the world make this

strategy less and less successful. The actor in rural areas need to apply new strategies based on mobilization and the interconnection of different fields , i.e. economy of scope Agriculture environment water, energy , local handicraft ,agro tourism and tourism organic agriculture ,local products direct on farm sales ,heritage and patrimony ,have to be combined in order to form a new territorial based production system , . Therefore ,it is necessary to redefine identities ,strategies ,practices and networks within the territory to overcome the current model of organization by single commodity chains and sector and redefine the territory as a competitive production unit based on economies of scope .

Important of farming

1. In rural area through the world ,agriculture represent the predominant land use and a major component of the viability of rural areas . farming and related activities make up the basic fabric of rural life contributing significantly to the overall state of rural regions in terms of employment and business opportunities infrastructure and quality of the environment .
2. The main potential contribution of farming to rural development are in terms of supporting employment ,ancillary businesses and environmental services in .in peripheral regions farming may be necessary to support the economic and social infrastructure .
3. In the context of agriculture reform ,WTO rules should contain sufficient to allow countries to

promote rural development ,especially to preserve social and political stability .

4. The degree to which farming represent a share of the rural economy . and hence its relative importance as a sector ,determines its potential economic contribution to rural development . In some countries ,farming may be the primary economic activity of of a region and support the vast majority of the population in employment .In such regions it is clear that overall social and political stability is inextricably linked with the condition of the agriculture sector .
5. Rural development policies should exploit the contribution of farming ,both in terms of improving on farming activities and supporting ancillary services ,to secure sustainable development for rural areas .
6. **Contribution to rural development**
1 Employment . In countries whose share of overall employment in agriculture is as high level , for example where farmers represent over 50% of the workforce farming is likely to be the key economic activity determining the progress of rural development . with such a substantial proportion of the labour force engage in agriculture , any policy which led to a swift and artificial reduction in employment could have disastrous consequences for the labour force and dependence , leading to social and political instability .
7. **Related economy**
The farm sector in every country supports a range of ancillary and service industries generating economic activity in supply and distribution chains as well as processing industries , where farming is the primary economic activity ,the entire rural economy ,including services such as health care education and basic infrastructure ,may depend on the profitability of the sector .
8. **In remote and peripheral areas** where society has verified a legitimate priority to prevent depopulation farming is likely to be one of a limited range of economic activities possible to maintain the economic viability of the sector .
9. **Envirolment and cultural services**
Farming may be contribute to rural development by promoting environment and cultural services to society . Agriculture development and rural development are related with each other .
10. **Agriculture and its contribution to poverty reduction** There is a lot of evidence that agriculture can contribute to poverty reduction beyond a direct effect on farmers' Incomes . Agriculture development can stimulate economic development outside of the agriculture sector , and lead to higher job and

growth creation . Increases productivity of agriculture raises farm incomes ,increases food supply ,reduces food prices ,and provides greater employments opportunities in both rural and urban areas .Higher income can increase the consumer demand for goods and services produced by sector other than agriculture . such linkage (or the multiplier effect) between growth in the agriculture sector and the wider economy has enabled developing countries to diversify to other sector where growth is higher and wages are better .

Importants of Agriculture in rural developments

1. **Rural and agricultural development and equitable distribution** of the benefits of economic growth are crucial for the global reduction of poverty and hunger . Numerous studies have provided evidence that the impact of economic growth on reducing hunger and poverty depends as much on the nature of the growth (i.e.. Industrial or rural economy based) as on its scale and speed .for example a world bank's analysis of data from India ,found that growth in rural areas and in the agriculture sector had a much greater impact on reducing poverty than did urban and industrial growth .
2. **The rural economy** plays an important role with regard to employment since the economic growth in urban centers is too slow to generate sufficient employment to absorb the migrated labour force ,particularly in transitions countries . The contribution of agriculture is obvious in rural areas where it is one of the major economic activity although small semi – urban center's plays a major role in the economic growth of rural areas . Therefore, employment in rural areas may depends heavily on agriculture and related sectors, especially in areas where tourism and the incentive to invest in the industry are very low
3. **Agriculture activities** can be crucial in the preservation of natural resources by maintaining agriculture and forestry activities environmental risk can be reduced and direct economic damage caused by avalanches ,landslides ,forest fires etc. Can be prevented .In addition in regions where tourism is an important economic factor .
4. **The efficiency and competitiveness of the rural sector** is dependent on a coherent approach regarding land tenure . land fragmentation is an important factor affectin many transition countries and its resolution through land consolidation would give young farmers in particular ,an intensive to invest in their holding and to remain in rural areas .
5. **Gender wise employment**

A glance as at the gender wise rural employment shows that the percentage of male workers engaged in agricultural activities declined from 78 per cent in 1983 to 53 per cent in 2018 ,while the rate of female agriculture

employment fell from 88 per cent to 71 per cent in the same period ,thus both male and female employment in the rural agriculture sector followed the same trend in selected states (see Table)

Rural Agriculture Employment %

States	1983(Male)	2018-19(Male)	1983 Female	2018-19 Female
Andhra Pradesh	77	50	83	74
Assam	79	41	80	49
Bihar	81	52	88	76
Gujrat	79	64	92	83
Haryana	71	35	90	61
Karnataka	82	57	88	73
Kerala	58	29	70	26
MP	87	68	94	80
Maharashtra	80	64	93	84
Odisha	78	47	81	60
Punjab	77	38	92	42
Rajasthan	81	56	94	82
TN	69	38	82	51
UP	79	58	90	81
WB	73	50	75	45
India	78	53	88	71

Note-Author’s compilation from NSS (1983) and PLEF (2018-19)

On the other hand, workforce participation in rural non –agriculture sectors for male workers increased from 22 per cent in 1983 to 47 per cent in 2018 ,thus registering an increase of 25 percentages points .Along similar lines ,female employments in the rural non-agriculture sector gradually increased from 12 per cent to 29 per cent over the same period .

6. **Rural development** allows the improvement of the population’s quality of life . Economic stability can be achieved through actions within the rural areas . In this sense ,agriculture is fundamental for the growth of a nation. Thus ,it is extremely important to improve the efficiency of resource use, promote R& D in the sector ,and reduce the environment impact .New technologies are needed to increase the productivity levels. Moreover ,agriculture and rural development can be used to fight the abandonment and depopulation of certain areas.

7. Sustainable agriculture Production

In attempting to ensure food security on a national level ,including urban residents ,it is important to obtain and maintain a certain degree of domestic production capacity in conjunction with imports and reserves .Also, in many developing countries ,agriculture holds an important position in spurring national economic development and acquiring foreign currency .

8. Stable food supply

Ensuring food security for an entire country ,including urban areas ,is based on combination of stabilizing and improving its own domestic agriculture production ,plus securing stable sources of imports and storing appropriate level of reserves .Improvements in policies ,rules regulation and systems as well as improvements in infrastructure like transportation and storage facilities are also required in order to supply imported or locally produced food to consumers.

9. Promoting dynamic rural communities

To eradicate poverty in rural areas and promote dynamic rural communities ,it is important to step up the empowerment of local resident ,such as promoting a variety of economic activities like handicraft and other small businesses ,improving and organizing rural infrastructure such as community roads and drinking water supply ,and raising health and education standards .This is all in addition to improving agriculture production and utilizing and selling agriculture products .Directly benefiting rural resident is also important from the perspective of achieving human security .

Conclusion

1. In other rural areas ,where farm employments accounts for a small portion of the workforce ,a broader approach to rural development and the

role of farming in the process including policies to diversify income sources ,may be needed .

2. Agriculture provides employment opportunities for rural people on a large scale in underdeveloped and developing countries . It is important source of livelihood .Generally ,landless workers and marginal farmers are engaged in non agricultural jobs like handicraft ,furniture ,textiles ,leather ,metal work , processing industries ,and in other service sector .These rural units fulfill merely local demands .in about 70.6% of total labour force depends upon agriculture
3. It is time that rural economy depends on agriculture and allied occupation in and underdeveloped country .The rising agriculture surplus caused by increasing agriculture production and productivity tends to improve social welfare ,partially in rural areas .The living standards of rural masses rises and they start consuming nutritious diet including eggs ,milk ,ghee and fruits .They lead a comfortable life having all modern amenities – a better house, motor cycle ,radio ,television and use of better clothes .

From the above cited explanation we conclude that agriculture development is must for the rural development and the economic development of the country . Agriculture process is essential to provide food for growing

non agriculture labour force ,raw materials for industrial production and saving and tax revenue to supports development of the rest of the economy .to earn foreign exchange and to provide a growing market for domestic manufactures .

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